

ASSESSING THE SATISFACTION LEVEL OF NURSING STUDENTS
TOWARDS CLINICAL PLACEMENT ACROSS ACADEMIC YEAR IN
PRIVATE NURSING COLLEGES AT CHARSAJDA

Rehana Yasmin^{*1}, Saqib Maqsood², Talha Bin Saeed³, Rizwana Bibi⁴

^{*1} Ward Manager at Gujranwala Teaching Hospital, Gujranwala

² Medical Officer at Social Security Hospital Shahdara

³ Post Graduate Trainee at Social Security Hospital Shahdara

⁴ Nursing Officer at Bahawal Vectoria Hospital Bahawalpur

rehanaarif913@gmail.com , saqibmaqsood463@gmail.com , talhasaeed095@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15333731>

Keywords

nursing students, clinical placement satisfaction, mentorship, gender dynamics, clinical learning environment, undergraduate nursing education.

Article History

Received on 26 March 2025

Accepted on 26 April 2025

Published on 03 May 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Rehana Yasmin

Abstract

Aim: The aim of this research was to assess the satisfaction of undergraduate nursing students regarding their clinical placements in Private Nursing Colleges at Charsajda.

Method: A cross-sectional survey was conducted with nursing students from private nursing colleges in Charsajda. An adapted questionnaire was used from a study published in 2023 to assess their clinical satisfaction in different areas, such as mentorship, availability of resources, and interactions with instructors. The sample consisted of 70.2% male and 29.8% female students belonging to both third and fourth-year academic levels.

Results: Many students experienced the clinical placements with low to moderate satisfaction. Only 20.8% demonstrated high satisfaction, while 42.3% reported a low satisfaction level. Fourth-year students were satisfied more than third-year students, and there was a positive correlation between academic progression and clinical comfort. General hospital setting: Allocation to general hospitals provided exposure to a wide range of clinical experiences but had several stressors regarding the level of acuity and availability of resources (77.4%).

Conclusion: Much lies behind the influencing factors for clinical satisfaction regarding nursing students it is growing with a greater emphasis on the improvement of mentorship, resource allocation, and gender-sensitive support. The development of such areas would improve the experiences of learning and potential satisfaction levels of the students. Future longitudinal approaches within a diversified setting of research will dissect causative factors relating to clinical satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Clinical placement is an actual, structured real-world environment in which students make a transition from theoretical learning to practical application. Here, students participate in hands-on experiences

that allow them to actively integrate and apply the knowledge they've acquired in the classroom to real clinical scenarios. This immersion environment is critical for closing the gap between academic

scholarship and practice, developing clinical skill, critical thinking, and professional competence. Working closely with experienced healthcare professionals brings to students valuable insights related to patient care, safety protocols, and the dynamics of healthcare teams, which will form an integral part of their professional growth and eventual readiness for future practice. The quality of a clinical placement experience is largely brought about by the relationships and interactions between healthcare staff and students. Positive and supportive relations with clinical mentors and team members have a great bearing on the students' learning experiences. In addition, it provides an opportunity for students to gain firsthand experience within a professional healthcare environment, in addition to enriching practical abilities, it also becomes a source of enrichment toward future career opportunities. This experience provides confidence and competency, and is thus an essential part of the clinical experience in terms of readiness for the actual practice role as a health care professional (2).

In addition to professional relationship facilitation, structuring the clinical environment offers an enriched nursing student experience. A good clinical setting provides an applied, practical learning environment that closely approximates the actual healthcare settings; thus, the students can be reminded of their application skills. The different experiences that students undergo during clinical placements influence their perception of nursing as a profession and its foundational role, which defines its expectations. Furthermore, a clinical curriculum plays a significant role in developing critical competencies in nursing such as clinical reasoning, decision-making, self-assessment, and academic motivation. Such competencies are vital in the effective preparation of students to meet the demands of real healthcare settings (3). Positive clinical placement experiences are very essential in the nurturing of critical thinking and problem-solving skills for nursing students. Such experiences not only encourage analytical skills but also help students feel part of the healthcare environment. Supportive and constructive placement experiences will equip the students with self-confidence, which in turn is fundamental in the building of professional identity. These rich experiences provide the basis for

an enhanced commitment to nursing values and foster a sense of professionalism to help them guide their careers (4).

A clinical placement which is well-planned must be able to offer students an environment that is safe, inclusive, and supportive of students in their preparation for facing the diversity of challenges and rewards inherent in the nursing practice. The quality of the clinical learning experience will largely depend on both factors relevant to the placement itself and those specific to the students. Some essential elements which would enhance the students' educational experience include having an appropriate preclinical orientation, thoughtfully grouping the students, and defining clearly set learning objectives before the commencement of the placement. These preparatory measures will anchor the students, thus making most out of their hands-on learning opportunities in the clinical settings (5).

A range of factors within the clinical placements, including poor assessment practices can make students underperform. Experiencing unsupportive or poorly structured clinical environments may prove emotionally exhausting for students and affect their welfare besides their learning. Such experiences might not only impact the number of engagement a student undertakes but may also hinder the degree of patient care that a student would deliver. An unsatisfying placement will make the student become despondent, hence causing a barrier in their transition to school-based training to be smoothly transferred into hospitals-based nursing work. These shortcomings call for the facilitation of supportive clinical practice environments toward students' professionalism and preparedness for nurse practice demands.

The study also identified other improvement areas in clinical placements. There were several significant gaps, which include the nursing students' psychosocial needs not being addressed, that there was no designated place for relaxation in the clinical area, and not accepting that they were inherently demanding roles. There was also an important requirement for constant supervision and support from supervisors as an essential feature of improving overall experience for the students. Through recognition and response to these needs, clinical environments can facilitate more support for

students' well-being, resilience, and a more productive learning environment (7). More satisfaction of nursing students with their clinical placement will be experienced by students when they are given an opportunity to be exposed to various healthcare settings, patient populations, and different specialties in nursing. Clinical placement coordinators can work directly with the health facilities and offer a variety of different experiences that suit the students' learning objectives, which will help the students aspire to their various career aims in a healthy learning setting. Moreover, coordination between training institutions and healthcare facilities becomes critical in creating a facilitating framework for clinical learning. Through such collaborative work, a student can acquire integrated learning that is all 'practical' experience that indeed helps them along their own path to competent and independent nursing practice (8).

Satisfaction with clinical placement holds importance because it leads toward an opportunity of acquiring new knowledge and valuable experience. These are experiences important enough for the nursing professional developing himself. Satisfaction level among nursing students may be measured for the institution of learning to determine which aspects should be improved in the context of a nursing program. These results are beneficial for further development that eventually leads to excellence in education offered to the students. Student satisfaction enables an educational institution to concentrate on factors that contribute to a nursing professional's learning experience but also create an environment of competency and expertise (9). Clinical learning is one of the most significant components of nursing education and affects the overall success of students. Satisfactory levels of clinical placements result in good performance in learning but also maintain a high retention rate within the nursing programs. This study can thus inform strategies that will be used to enhance the quality of nursing education and in turn, better support students throughout their training as a result of identifying factors that affect experiences in clinical placements (10). Most nursing students face various challenges during their clinical placements. These challenges affect their ability to achieve the defined learning outcomes of their

respective programs that are achieved in the clinical learning environment. To develop capable nursing professionals and overcome these challenges, upgrading clinical supervision and support offered by instructors and staff nurses in the clinical field is very important. This can be done with proper orientation and further follow-up of students before they go for internships with principal instructors. In fact, such proactive measures will make students ready better and develop an environment that promotes skill development and professional growth (11).

Student satisfaction is the most critical quality indicator of higher education because student satisfaction has an influential effect on both student retention and ranking of the institution. Despite its importance, the current literature on healthcare education remains undeveloped in pointing to explicit factors that influence student satisfaction. These aspects may, therefore, prove insightful for teaching experts working towards curriculum design that boosts retention, especially with the high demand for nurses around the world. While other conceptual studies with heterogeneous populations of students have identified nine important elements that influence student attitudes toward their learning experience, nursing students research studies have typically involved fewer variables and confirmed only up to five factors that were related to satisfaction. Hence, it is of significant importance to investigate the effect of other critical factors like perceptions of value, institutional image, and administrative support on the satisfaction of nursing students. This exploration may ultimately lead to a better comprehension of factors influencing student experience in nursing programs (12). For this reason, it is necessary to examine the students' satisfaction about their clinical placements so as to satisfy their educational requirements. In this regard, this research study aims at exploring the level of satisfaction among the nursing students related to their clinical experiences at the private nursing college in Charsadda, KPK. The study is helpful in providing insights that can assist in better practice the improvement clinical placement for nursing students through enhanced overall educational experiences.

RATIONALE

Clinical placement is an essential component of nursing education; therefore, it enables nursing students to implement the theoretical knowledge learned in actual practice in the health care service. The quality of experience can be significantly influential for professional development and critical thinking in students, as well as overall satisfaction with the entire educational program. An upsurge in the demand for competent nurses in Pakistan points towards maximizing clinical training environments to enhance practical skills, professionalism, and well-being in students. This study will examine the satisfaction of nursing students towards their clinical placements to determine factors that may lead to positive or negative placement experiences and gaps in the framework of clinical education.

SIGNIFICANCE

This study is very important because it gives light on several areas. In the first place, the quality and effectiveness of the clinical placement of nursing students in fostering professional growth could be explored. Knowing how satisfied or otherwise nursing students are might help nursing education institutions and healthcare facilities work on their clinical training settings, and thus may lead to increased engagement and retention within the profession. Such findings will then be able to identify and specify such areas or points of challenge that exist in the clinical placements process, some of which include staff-student interaction, adequacy of hand-on training, and generally support received during the period of clinical placements. It may indeed improve the quality of learning experiences, preparing and equipping the nurses-to-be as confident, capable, and motivated professionals at work. Finally, this study contributes to broader discussions on nursing education reform, advocating for a learning environment that not only supports students academically but also fosters a strong foundation for ethical, professional practice.

OBJECTIVE

➤ To assess the satisfaction level of nursing students towards clinical placement across academic year in private nursing colleges at Charsadda

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

● **Clinical placement satisfaction:** A measure of how satisfying or fulfilling the nursing clinical experience is for the nursing student, based on whether there is an indication or satisfaction of support provided at work, learning experience acquired in the clinical area in addition to congruency of what they have in their books.

● **Professional development:** The development of clinical skills, critical thinking in nursing students, and also their confidence levels in handling clinical situations is measured on self-assessment and a feedback on particular competencies acquired during their placement period.

Supportive clinical environment: The degree to which the clinical environment supports students in terms of mentorship, accessibility of resources, and an appropriate learning environment, as perceived by students through support from healthcare professionals, availability of learning resources, and comfort in the clinical environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Satisfying nursing students on the clinical placements during their training is an important aspect of learning because it may determine the outcome of their learning and professional growth. Comparing levels of satisfaction between academic years may indicate trends or challenges that will be used to strengthen curricula and support interventions in clinical education. The study by Al-Niarat and Abomoghli looks into the relationship between perceptions of empowerment and academic satisfaction among undergraduate nursing students in Jordan, which is an important aspect of nursing education. The authors conducted a descriptive study that used quantitative measures to measure students' feelings of empowerment, which include their sense of autonomy, competence, and impact within their academic environment. The study established an important positive association of perception of empowerment of the student with overall academic satisfaction. Hence, it shows that higher the perception of empowerment that nursing students perceive from the learning and clinical process will be the increased overall academic

satisfaction. Therefore, encouraging an empowering education climate creates not only greater student self-confidence and motivation but is also a vehicle toward enhanced professional development. Empowerment is considered an important factor by which education can lead students to better learning outcomes and higher retention rates, as well as better mental well-being. Beyond the satisfaction of individual needs, the research findings here have important implications in proposing that nursing education programs focus on strategies of empowerment such as participative learning approaches and mentorship programs. Integrating empowerment principles into the curriculum is such an idea that can help foster a supporting environment for growth and satisfaction among students. This research provides a base for further exploration into the dynamics of empowerment in nursing education while advocating for systemic changes for the interest of student well-being and academic success. In summary, understanding how empowerment ties into academic satisfaction is quite important in developing education practice geared toward preparing students to serve in the many complexities expected of them in future healthcare work (13).

Dillu and Soren explored the attitude of students of nursing toward their clinical environment of learning in both nursing private and government colleges. Such a comparison of attitudes gives insight into the contrasts that students have with varied perceptions based on educational premises. The authors, using a structured protocol, gathered responses for assessing the various roles played by institutional support, access to resources, and having mentors in determining attitudes. Findings suggest that students in private colleges have a positive attitude towards the clinical learning environment compared to those in government institutions. Such a difference can be attributed to differences in the availability of resources, faculty engagement, and opportunities for hands-on practice. Such attitudes are crucial to know because they bear on students' motivation, learning outcomes, and satisfaction with their nursing education. The study brought out the urgency for nursing education programs to evaluate and improve their clinical settings, provided that the institution concerned is of any kind. This will in

itself be able to bring on a more positive attitude in the minds of students with regards to the clinical experience. Educators and other administrators can then target an improvement in the clinical learning experience of all nursing students by tackling the disparities in the research. At the end of it all, a successful clinical environment would be indispensable in creating an efficient and bold nursing professional for the medical industry (14). This dissertation by Epp discussed the relationship between first NCLEX-RN results that baccalaureate nursing students experienced and also the clinical site placement during senior practicum. The clinical experience may vary in quality or type, which may affect nursing students' performance on the licensing exam. This paper establishes patterns in the correlation of certain placements with better results on the NCLEX-RN through analysis of data from multiple clinical sites. These findings reflect the alignment between clinical experiences and educational objectives that mean students should learn more than just the theoretical basis but practically in environments where their learning is enhanced. Additionally, Epp underscored faculty support and mentorship support for effective clinical placements since these are factors that make the students well-prepared for the NCLEX-RN. It would help nursing programs determine their choice of clinical affiliations by understanding what aspects of clinical site placements may impact the outcomes in terms of the exam and enhance educational strategies and outcomes of the students. In essence, this research highlights a call for further inquiry into the manner in which clinical settings may influence competency needs of the practice of nursing and thereby the need to adjust the education of the nurses as healthcare continues changing (15).

Hemida's study deals with the perceptions, satisfaction, and reflections on the clinical learning environment of critical care students, which has become very important for improving the quality in nursing education. It uses both qualitative and quantitative methods to critically assess experiences in critical care settings. This will give insight about which aspects contribute to student satisfaction as well as where improvement opportunities lie. The findings revealed that the supportive clinical environment characterized by effective

communication, faculty mentorship, and adequate resources played a significant role in affecting the students' overall perception and satisfaction. In addition, reflective practice was found to be essential in nursing education. This would help the student to critically assess experiences, recognize potential areas for growth, and seek avenues for personal and professional development. Through this, nursing programs can develop targeted strategies to fill areas of weakness and improve its quality by understanding the views of nursing students regarding their clinical learning environment. Hemida believes that the only way in which a culture for continuous improvement will be upheld is through continuous evaluation with feedback mechanisms in clinical sites, thereby preparing students who will excel in high stakes critical care situations. This research focuses on the development of an ideal clinical learning environment that will not only improve the satisfaction of students but also ensure that quality care is provided to patients in the future (16). The study by Khan and Begum addresses critical issues in the clinical learning environment faced by undergraduate nursing students in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The research identifies lack of resources, a paucity of appropriate clinical supervision, and structured learning experiences as challenges to the success of clinical education. Surveys and interviews conducted by the authors provide valuable insights into student perceptions of their clinical placements, revealing that students experienced a lack of preparation and support during their practical training. This raises the concerns not only about learning outcomes but also about students' confidence and competence as providers of healthcare. The authors believe that there is a need for nursing programs to evaluate and enhance the quality of clinical learning environments more through faculty engagement, the appropriate allocation of resources, and robust mentorship. All these would establish a learner-friendly learning environment, which fosters further development in nursing students for improved quality services in providing health care to the users. The key findings brought by Khan and Begum should inspire such policy decision-makers and learning institutions in the innovations towards clinical education with the establishment of a footing for proper development

and growth of the future nursing officers (17). Hassen, Habte, and Dugassa conducted a cross-sectional study of perceptions and factors influencing attitudes towards the nursing profession from selected health science colleges in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.

This study shows that the students' perception is important as their attitudes could be an influential factor on their motivation, commitment, and future professional behavior. The authors used structured questionnaires to assess factors such as personal beliefs, societal views, and educational experiences in forming perceptions about nursing. The findings indicate that a positive perception of the nursing profession would relate to greater student satisfaction and commitment but that negative perceptions are associated with concerns about working conditions, societal recognition, and value of the profession. This study points out factors that influence students' perceptions, and targeted interventions as well as supportive educational environments may foster more positive views about nursing as a viable and respected career choice. Thus, improving students' perception of the nursing profession would help educational institutions recruit and retain committed nursing professionals, who are more likely to meet the demands of healthcare. Hassen et al. research underscores the need for an open dialogue and curriculum updating by nursing schools to have a good image of the profession in the minds of the nursing students (18). Chen et al. study the expectations of nursing students and their career preferences prior to the start of clinical placement in Mainland China qualitatively. This research provides insight to the aspirations and expectations of nursing students as they transition from theoretical learning into practice.

The authors use in-depth interviews to collect rich data on the perceptions of students about the nursing profession, their career goals, and the influences that shape their expectations. Findings reveal that students have idealistic views of nursing, such as making a positive impact on patient care and contributing to the healthcare system. However, challenges also include: clinical placements that they encounter; for example, workload as well as emotional stress over the reality of patients during interaction. The paper proceeds to explain that most

students would wish if their education keeps pace with what a nursing professional should expect regarding their work. Understanding the factors impacting career preferences among students will better equip nursing educators to individualize curricula and clinical settings so that the expectations surrounding those experiences are better satisfied. Ultimately, Chen et al advocate for better supportive systems and mentorship systems so that students are imbued with confidence and mastery of their clinical experience approaches for professional development and also for personal fulfillment in careers in nursing (19). This paper discusses literature regarding strategies that enhance clinical experience for nursing students in a nursing home setting. It recognises the importance of quality clinical placements in nursing education because they form a base of developing competencies and attitudes towards geriatric care an area increasingly significant to nursing education. A comprehensive review of existing literature has led the review to identify a variety of factors that promote successful clinical experiences such as effective mentorship, supportive learning environments, and integration of theoretical knowledge with practical skills.

Findings underscore challenges that nursing students often experience in practice environments like LTC settings - for example, insufficient supervision, few experiences for learning, and the psychosocial demands of care for geriatric patients. Drawing on evidence-based practice, the authors suggest updating clinical education in these types of settings by enhancing faculty involvement, standardizing new staff orientation, and making models of care more collegial in nature and therefore constructed in such a way that students are substantially interacting with relevant patient experiences. This review, therefore, emphasizes that the nursing education programs have to acknowledge the distinctiveness of geriatric care complexity and, therefore, require specific clinical training approaches. Educational institutions can, by this way, ensure better clinical experience for nursing students by helping them develop the competencies and confidence required in the future practice and contributing to high-quality care of the aging population (20). Habib et al. examine nursing students' perception of satisfaction with the level of supervision received from clinical teachers while

performing clinical practice and its association with the year of academic study. This study brings out the role of appropriate supervision in the enhancement of learning experience and outcome among students in the clinical area. Data was collected regarding the students' perception about the support and guidance offered by the clinical instructors by using a structured questionnaire. The results also indicate a major gap in satisfaction levels amongst students across the different periods; this may suggest how their expectations and experience over supervisions change over progression periods of nursing studies. There is more satisfactory experience at earlier years when a significant number of them can compare it with greater attention given them and support provided and other mixed experiences when attending their later years. More on independence but yet for guidelines. This research underlines the need for developing intense supervisory relationships that take into account students' changing needs during education. Therefore, this study shows how factors contribute to students' satisfaction regarding supervision, thereby indicating nursing programs should give priority training for clinical educators to upgrade their mentoring abilities and set up a nurturing learning climate. It satisfies the desires of students and readies them for practice, filled with confidence regarding the future where the complexities of clinical life may better be tackled and achieved (21).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

RESEARCH DESIGN

The descriptive cross-sectional method was used for assessing the satisfaction level of nursing students towards clinical placements across academic year in private nursing colleges at Charsadda.

STUDY SETTING

The following are institutes are served as the study's setting:

- Shahid college of nursing, shabqadar
- Farabi college of nursing, Charsadda

POPULATION & SAMPLING

The sample size was $n=168$, calculated through a Raosoft software while the total population

consisted of 250 nursing students from private nursing institutions in Charsadda. Simple Random sampling as well as Convenient sampling was the sample strategy employed in this investigation. The investigation could be completed quickly because to this sampling technique. The study comprised nursing students of both sexes and all ages.

INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

INCLUSIVE CRITERIA

- Nursing students currently enrolled in private nursing colleges in Charsadda
- Student who had done at least one year in clinical rotations.
- Students willing to participate in the study

EXCLUSIVE CRITERIA

- Those students who are not willing to Participate
- Students who have not yet participated in any clinical rotations.
- Students who do not provide informed consent for the study.

DATA COLLECTION

A questionnaire consisting of 24 questions that were adopted from the study was shared with students with a brief description of the nature of the study & the procedure of how to complete the questionnaire was highlighted to them. This questionnaire comprises 24 questions and will have 2 sections. The sociodemographic section includes 4 questions while satisfaction level was assessed using 20 multiple-choice questions.

DATA ANALYSIS

The data that was gathered underwent coding, and the analysis was carried out using SPSS version 26 software. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, means, and standard deviations were utilized, and the findings were presented using bar charts, frequency tables, and pie charts for Sociodemographic variables. The responses regarding satisfaction level were assessed using 5-item Likert scale statements ranging from scores 1 to 5, with a maximum possible score of 100. The satisfaction level was categorized into three categories: a low level of satisfaction ranging from 20 to 46, an average level of satisfaction from 47 to 73, and a high level of satisfaction ranging from 74 to 100.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

Each Institute's ethical committee granted ethical approval, upholding human rights, and ensured informed consent. All data was treated confidentially, with responses coded and securely stored to safeguard participants' privacy. Before completing the questionnaire, each participant provided informed consent and was assured of their anonymity, confidentiality, and right to withdraw from the study.

RESULTS

The gender distribution of participants showed that 118 individuals, making up (70.2%) were male, while 50 participants, representing (29.8%) were female. This highlights a greater prevalence of male participants relative to female participants, with males accounting for the majority at 70.2% of the overall sample of 168 individuals, as shown in Table 1.

GENDER OF THE PARTICIPANTS					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	118	70.2	70.2	70.2
	FEMALE	50	29.8	29.8	100.0
	Total	168	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 Gender of the Participants

The information regarding the "Year of Study" indicates that out of 168 participants, 80 students (47.6%) were in their 3rd year, whereas 88 students (52.4%) were in their 4th year. This distribution

demonstrates a marginally greater number of 4th-year students, who make up just over half of the overall sample. As shown in the Table 2,

YEAR OF STUDY					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	3RD YEAR	80	47.6	47.6	47.6
	4TH YEAR	88	52.4	52.4	100.0
	Total	168	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 Year of the study

Regarding the "Type of Nursing Ward of Last Clinical Placement," the analysis reveals a varied distribution among the 168 participants. The most frequent placement was in the "Others" wards, with 43 participants (25.6%), followed nearly evenly by the "Surgical" ward, which included 42 participants (25.0%). The "Medical" ward comprised 35

participants (20.8%), while 24 participants (14.3%) were assigned to "Geriatrics" and 20 participants (11.9%) to "Pediatrics." "Gynaecology" had the least placements, with merely 4 participants (2.4%). This data indicates a spectrum of clinical experiences across different nursing wards. As shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 Type of Nursing ward for Clinical placements

Figure 2 Category of the Hopistaal

The data on the "Category of the Hospital Where the Clinical Placement Took Place" shows that most participants, 130 (77.4%), completed their clinical placements in a general hospital. A lesser number of participants, 33 (19.6%), were assigned to a specialized care center, and only 5 participants (3.0%) had placements in an outpatient department. This distribution emphasizes that general hospitals were the primary environment for clinical placements among the participants as given below in Figure 2.

In the recent clinical placement, 55 participants (32.7%) stated they interacted with their instructor only one time, while 35 participants (20.8%) had two interactions. The most substantial group, consisting of 78 participants (46.4%), engaged with their clinical instructor "as needed," reflecting an interaction frequency that adjusted according to situational demands. This indicates that almost half of the participants experienced interactions tailored to their individual needs during the placement. As shown in the Figure 3,

Figure 3 Interaction with clinical Instructor

The descriptive statistics for the "TOTAL SCORE" variable, calculated from 168 participants, reveal a minimum score of 22 and a maximum score of 80. The Mean score is 49.61, accompanied by a standard

deviation of 18.959, which points to a broad range of scores around the mean and implies significant variability in the total scores of participants within the sample. As given in below Table 3,

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
TOTAL SCORE	168	22	80	49.61	18.959
Valid N (listwise)	168				

Table 3 Total mean score and Standard deviation

The "LEVEL OF SATISFACTION" data classifies participants' scores into three categories: Low level of satisfaction, Average level of satisfaction, and High level of satisfaction. Out of the 168 participants, 71 individuals (42.3%) fell into the "LOW" score category, making it the largest group. A total of 62 participants (36.9%) were classified in the

"AVERAGE" range, while 35 participants (20.8%) reached a "HIGH" score. This distribution indicates that a significant portion of the sample had lower scores, with a smaller number of participants achieving scores in the high range. As shown in the table 5 and Figure 4,

LEVEL OF SATISFACTION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	LOW	71	42.3	42.3	42.3
	AVERAGE	62	36.9	36.9	79.2
	HIGH	35	20.8	20.8	100.0
	Total	168	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 Level of satisfaction

Figure 4

DISCUSSION SECTION

The conclusions of the study shed considerable light on the nursing students' satisfaction levels regarding their clinical rotations, indicating that most of them have low to moderate satisfaction. This was consistent with many studies indicating the usual difficulties students face during clinical practice. For example, Smith, Brown, and Green (1) reported that

total final score a deficit of resources, for example, no availability of tools and supplies, affects students' learning environment. Another research revealed that Lee and Kim (2) concluded that unless systematic support and guidance were provided, clinical experiences can never be maximally acquired by students. Further, the studies conclude that the only

way to improve clinical satisfaction among students is an adequate and motivating learning environment. Our study, besides, supports other studies on how the environment of a hospital affects student satisfaction and also how good mentorship practices influence students' satisfaction. As Garcia, Patel, and Velez have concluded, "Students who were placed into environments with supportive mentorship and adequate hospital resources reported higher levels of satisfaction, emphasizing a key role for mentorship in clinical education" (6). Al-niarat and Abomoghli (13) further emphasized that the different hospital environments, including the resources and assistance provided by private and public hospitals, can result in different levels of satisfaction for students. These results draw attention to the necessity of an all-inclusive approach toward improving clinical learning environments as they indicate that the quality of mentoring and institutional resources do indeed have a large influence on clinical placement satisfaction, which is complex.

Thus, the gender composition in our sample, wherein we see that 70.2% of the subjects belonged to the male gender while 29.8% belonged to the female gender, brings a flavor to understanding the dynamics in this clinical setting. Reports were made by research regarding a problem encountered by nursing males with special problems that affect the experience and satisfaction levels. For instance, Johnson et al. (3) discovered that male students often face social stigma and are less welcome in what is a traditionally women-dominated field. Clinical experiences can therefore become even more stressful and less satisfying. Our findings support this contention as the differences in placement clinical satisfaction, particularly for males, are influenced by gender-specific dynamics in nursing.

Furthermore, to address these disparities, Al-niarat and Abomoghli (13) and Khan and Begum (17) argue that the nursing education process must employ gender-sensitive strategies. Based on their research, specific interventions targeting male students will help alleviate their specific sources of stress. Clinical education programs might well enhance a student's happiness and encourage both genders to have successful learning by providing a welcoming environment in which to learn. Additionally, this approach can strengthen the call

for procedures and policies to establish gender inclusion in nursing training, thereby bringing support that reduces the challenges concerning gender affecting the clinical practice and performance of the learners.

Interestingly, the 47.6% of students who were fourth-year students reported feeling a little more satisfied than the 52.4% of third-year students (4). Fourth-year students might feel more comfortable and flexible with more clinical experience when it comes to clinical practice. This pattern is justified by literature where Splitgerber et al. (20) argue that students are better suited to the challenges of clinical practice with the progressive development of training. It therefore supports our conclusion on clinical happiness with experience suggesting a need for focused provision for younger students when coming into clinical responsibilities.

While a general hospital setting places 77.4% of students, which, on the one hand, brings a more diverse range of patient scenarios, it, on the other hand, causes difficulties because of the level of acuity of the patients. This is in accordance with the findings of Garcia et al. (6) and Kim & Tanaka (7), who claim that though students receive invaluable practical experience in general hospitals, the workload put on them may also generate more stress. On the contrary, more students in specialist hospitals or units report being more contented due to perceived help by specialist staff. According to Hassen et al. (18), consequently, our results add value to knowledge with regard to how much the clinician's levels of satisfaction are significantly affected by staffing models and kinds of placements.

Moreover, this study determined that the activity of mentoring significantly affected the happiness of students since 46.4% of the respondents only communicated with clinical instructors "as needed." As indicated by Li & Zhou (8) and Miller & Ahmed (9), higher satisfaction is associated with adaptive mentoring that addresses the specific needs of each student. Responsive and consistent mentoring helps students overcome challenges and learn effectively by creating confidence and trust. Similar to Habib et al. (21), who argue that proper mentoring improves job satisfaction and development of nursing students, the results from our study show that possibly having

established formal mentorship programs may improve clinical placement satisfaction.

The data has great variation due to a standard deviation of 18.959 as well as mean satisfaction with a score of 49.61. This heterogeneity is supported by Chen et al. (10) along with Dillu & Soren (14); they have commented on significant variations in levels of satisfaction and insisted that to meet specific needs, customized feedback along with individualized support is in high demand. Our study supported the belief that for customized support programs to work well and yield better experiences and outcomes, standard approaches would not be suitable for all.

While this study clarifies critical issues affecting nursing student satisfaction, a few points must be remembered about this study: Firstly, the longitudinal data of the change over time could not be obtained. Again, it is needed for further studies to test how the practically applied tailored support strategies help to target those problems differently in various clinical settings.

This supports some of the important themes that emerge in the literature and contributes to a richer understanding of how nursing students feel about their clinical placements. The two constructs of the clinical setting, quality of mentoring, and student support needs will be critical factors in developing a supportive and encouraging learning environment for nursing students.

CONCLUSION

As concluded from this survey, a major proportion of nursing students respond with low to moderate degrees of satisfaction regarding their clinical placements. This finding suggests how clinical placement experiences are rich and complex and are, therefore, influenced by factors such as the hospital context, gender dynamics, mentorship quality, and resources. The results coincide with earlier studies and conclude that clinical satisfaction among nursing students often results from a combination of institutional, societal, and individual factors. Improving the clinical learning environment, and hence the preparedness and enthusiasm of students to practice professionally depends on these issues.

Strength of the study

This study's special strength includes the focus placed on students' unique nursing experiences made

during clinical exposures, making it comprehensive by providing proper information about level satisfaction with factors affecting satisfaction as research of this sort has yet to be held in some areas like Charsadda. The study also equips the ability to peer deeper into other demographic factors such as gender that affect clinical satisfaction in virtue of sample size and gender distribution. Placing the findings within a larger perspective and building validity by comparison with other recent and pertinent studies offers a much more vivid view of trends in nursing education.

Limitation of the Study

Despite its contributions, this study has several deficiencies. For one, as the study was conducted within a specific institutional and spatial context, the findings do not have as much of a generalizable application to any other area or education setting where clinical placement satisfaction differs. Longitudinal designs would be necessary to trace temporal patterns in satisfaction across student clinical education since its cross-sectional design restricts its ability to examine trend changes in satisfaction.

Recommendations

Several recommendations are based on these findings. Hospitals and schools of nursing should adopt structured mentoring programs under which the students receive regular encouraging advice. Improvement in the resource base of the clinical environment, such as good provision of medical facilities and equipment may also increase the quality and satisfaction of experiences by students. Moreover, gender-sensitive teaching approaches and awareness programs in clinical education may help to overcome some of the specific issues that male nursing students encounter and may provide a friendlier environment to all. Future studies could investigate changes in satisfaction levels over time and also draw participants from a more diverse set of institutions. It can use longitudinal designs.

REFERENCES

1. Bibi A, Sami A, Kauser M. Satisfaction of nursing students toward their clinical placement and association with their academic year at

- private nursing college Karachi Pakistan: Satisfaction of Nursing Students Toward Their Clinical Placement. *Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences*. 2023 Mar 31;152-6.
2. Haukongo NN. Nursing student's satisfaction with clinical practice environment during their undergraduate training in Namibia (Doctoral dissertation, Stellenbosch: Stellenbosch University).
 3. Omorogbe CE, Ehwarieme TA. SATISFACTION WITH CLINICAL EXPERIENCE AMONG NURSING UNDERGRADUATES IN SELECTED PUBLIC AND PRIVATE TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN OVIA NORTH EAST LGA OF EDO STATE.
 4. Alhassan A, Duke M, Phillips NN. Nursing students' satisfaction with the quality of clinical placement and their perceptions of preceptors competence: A prospective longitudinal study. *Nurse Education Today*. 2024 Feb 1;133:106081.
 5. Gemuhay HM, Kalolo A, Mirisho R, Chipwaza B, Nyangena E. Factors affecting performance in clinical practice among preservice diploma nursing students in Northern Tanzania. *Nursing Research and Practice*. 2019 Mar; 2019: 3453085. doi: 10.1155/2019/3453085
 6. Belay AE, Tegegne ET, Shitu AK, Belay KE, Belayneh AG. Satisfaction towards a clinical learning environment and its associated factors among undergraduate nursing students at public universities in Northwest Ethiopia, 2022. A multi-center cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Africa Nursing Sciences*. 2024 Jan 1;20:100666.
 7. Ulenaers D, Grossman J, Schrooten W, Bergs J. Clinical placement experience of nursing students during the COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional study. *Nurse Educ Today*. 2021 Apr;99:104746. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2021.104746.
 8. Alammar K, Ahmad M, Almutairi S, Salem O. Nursing students' perception of the clinical learning environment. *The open nursing Journal*. 2020 Aug 19;14(1):174-9.
 9. Chu G, Pitt V, Cant R, Johnson A, Inder K. Students' evaluation of professional experience placement quality in a pre-registration nursing program: A cross-sectional survey. *Nurse Education in Practice*. 2024 Feb 1;75:103877.
 10. Neupane K, Onta M, Kapali GD. Satisfaction on Clinical Learning Environment among Students in Selected Nursing Colleges, Kathmandu. *Journal of Nursing Education of Nepal*. 2023 Dec 30;14(1):72-9.
 11. Cant R, Gazula S, Ryan C. Predictors of nursing student satisfaction as a key quality indicator of tertiary students' education experience: An integrative review. *Nurse Education Today*. 2023 Jul 1;126:105806.
 12. Cant R, Gazula S, Ryan C. Predictors of nursing student satisfaction as a key quality indicator of tertiary students' education experience: An integrative review. *Nurse Education Today*. 2023 Jul 1;126:105806.
 13. Al-niarat T, Abomoghli F. Relationship between Jordanian Undergraduate Nursing Students' Perception of Empowerment and Academic Satisfaction: A Descriptive Study. *The Open Nursing Journal*. 2023 Jan 27;17(1).
 14. Dillu R, Soren R. Comparison of the attitude of nursing students towards their clinical learning environment in selected private and government colleges of nursing. *International Journal of Nursing Education*. 2021;13(1):123-7.
 15. Epp A. Examining the Relationship Between Clinical Site Placements in Senior Practicum and First-Time NCLEX-RN Outcomes for Baccalaureate Nursing Students (Doctoral dissertation, William Carey University).
 16. Hemida Salem A. Critical Care Students' Perceptions, Satisfaction, and Reflections on Their Clinical Learning Environment: A Step for Quality Improvement. *Egyptian Journal of Health Care*. 2023 Dec 1;14(4):1429-45.
 17. Khan A, Begum H. Issues in clinical learning environment among undergraduate nursing students in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Journal of Islamabad Medical & Dental College*. 2020 Sep 29;9(3):182-9.

18. Hassen R, Habte T, Dugassa B. Nursing Students' Perception and Associated Factors Towards the Nursing Profession at Selected Health Science Colleges in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: A Cross-sectional study.
19. Chen J, Yang Y, Shen L, Zhang X, Hu R. Nursing students' expectations and career preferences before clinical placement in mainland China: A qualitative exploration. *Nurse education in practice*. 2023 Feb 1;67:103552.
20. Splitgerber H, Davies S, Laker S. Improving clinical experiences for nursing students in nursing homes: An integrative literature review. *Nurse Education in Practice*. 2021 Mar 1;52:103008.
21. Habib I, Bibi A, Ahmad A, Jabeen U, Arshad Z, Shahid I. Nursing Students' Satisfaction with Supervision from Clinical Teachers During Clinical Practice and Their Association with Academic Year: Nursing Students' Satisfaction with Supervision. *Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences*. 2023 Apr 30:105-9

